

Site: SPHINX TEMPLE Season GS 79-80

Area: N. COLONNADE Square R16A1 Locus Number 4a

Progress of Excavation 26/II/80: Removed 4a across extent in R16A1

Shows subtly splotchy w/ concentrations more clay-like, other spots hit more sandy textured. Removed w/ trowel
2/II/80 R16A2: Shows here very similar to 4 on surface - more concentrated only slightly
tan clay. Mortar (white speckled) shows in spots on surface along edge F Balk and spot toward W side deposit (see plan). Large limestone piece which chipped in 4 but embedded in 4a looks to be corner fragment 4a seems to slope up slightly to S.T. N Wall. 4a has lenses of crusty mortar (as opposed to ^{pure} gypsum) frags ~ 5.6 cm above surface →

Locus Description COMPACT TAN CLAY

Location in Square See Plan R16A1

Under Locus 4 BROWN SAND WITH STONE RUBBLE Over Locus 4b BUFF GYPSUM (with clay admixture?)

Locus Dimensions _____

Levels 8.26 - 8.16

Analysis of non-artifactual materials Some small granite, dolomite, alabaster frags; Carbon spots, few larger limestone frags
1 smooth shiny object looks to be like animal claw(?)
Registered as object. 1 or 2 mud spots (grey alluvial)

2/II/80 (cont.)

(4b). (See E Balk). No sherds (couple ceramic splinters), Few granite, etc. chips. Stone material sifted out very fine limestone chips some fine granite, alabaster chips but few. Mortar spots which showed on surface (4a) actually large frags of pinkish white speckled mortar embedded in (4b).